

Bibliographic Relationships: From Principles to Practice

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Abstract

This research work is an experiment with the latest theory of bibliographic relationships as proposed by Murray & Tillett and is known as graph-friendly theory for biblio-cultural relationships. It sets objectives to develop a prototype digital archive of cultural text in an Indian language with the provision for bibliographic relationships based navigation to support the new user task 'to explore' included in IFLA-LRM, discusses groundbreaking theories of bibliographic relationships from the time of Panizzi to date, formulates research questions that are related to developing the prototype, and finally demonstrates the navigational framework through biblio-cultural relationships by using an array of open source software and open standards.

Keywords: Bibliographic relationships; Biblio-cultural relationships; Graph theory; Information visualization; GLAM

1. Introduction

Bibliographic relationships exist in resource description right from the time of Panizzi but formalized by Barbara Tillett in late 1980s. Since then many researchers have explored different facets of bibliographic relationships and have investigated possible roles of bibliographic relationships in retrieval of library resources. Moreover, the groundbreaking bibliographic data models like LRM – Library Reference Model (a seamless integration of FRBR – Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records, FRAD – Functional Requirements for Authority Data, FRISAD – Functional Requirements for Subject Authority Data), BIBFRAME, XOBIS, FOAF and BIBO & FaBiO have emphasized importance of bibliographic relationships. Bibliographic data formats like CCF, UNIMARC, MARC 21 family of standards, and DCMES (the global De-facto generic metadata standard) include different instances of bibliographic relationships. The latest cataloguing code – the RDA centres around the trinity of bibliographic universe – an entity, attributes of an entity and relationships of an entity with other entities. The latest updates of RDA shows development of relationship matrix for all FRBR entities and relationships as depicted in IFLA-LRM model.

The objectives of cataloguing have included recently two additional user tasks apart from the three fundamental tasks as proposed by Cutter in 1876 – to find, to identify, to select (Brunt, 1998). These two newly introduced user tasks are – 'to obtain' and 'to explore' as given in IFLA-LRM (Riva, 2016). The user task 'to explore' is aimed to discovering related bibliographic resources through relationships. It is possibly the most open ended user task in the

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Fig. 1: Trinity of bibliographic universe in RDA (source: RDA beta toolkit)

five interrelated users tasks as proposed in IFLA-LRM. This user task can only be supported through a concerted efforts like – i) making bibliographic relationship explicit; ii) developing facilities to visualize relationships; and iii) supporting easy navigation features on the basis of visualized relationships in retrieval interface.

2. Objectives

This research work is an attempt to develop mechanisms to visualize bibliographic relationships in a library retrieval interface supporting graphical navigational facilities to help end users in retrieving related resources. The specific objectives are as follows:

- 2.1 To develop a prototype digital archive of classical cultural text in an Indic script (Bengali script based documents in Unicode format) by extending some of the identified bibliographic relationships for dynamic linking of related objects available in a digital archive;
- 2.2 To design the prototype by applying – a) graph theory based bibliographic relationships model as developed by R. J. Murray and B. B. Tillett in 2011 (Murray & Tillett, 2011) as the theoretical base for the framework; and b) an array of open source software for the practical implementation of the theoretical framework; and
- 2.3 To facilitate enhanced information retrieval where both bibliographic resources and cultural resources are integrated by adding required relationships as per the needs of a digital

archive to support visualization of relationships for providing facility to navigate resource to resource in a lightbox with zoom-in feature.

This research work now needs to set the background with special emphasis on the origin and development of the concept of 'bibliographic relationship' as reflected in the works of researchers, types of bibliographic relationships as formalized by Barbara Tillett (Tillett, 1991, 2001), as refined by Smiraglia (Leazer & Smiraglia, 1996; Smiraglia & Leazer, 1999) and as extended by Vellucci (Vellucci, 1997a).

3. Genesis of Bibliographic Relationships

The concept of bibliographic relationships exists in almost every cataloguing theory and each cataloguing code in the name of collocation. Researchers in the domain of library cataloguing reported that there are two fundamental functions of a library catalogue – finding function and collocation function. The collocation function may be considered as the forerunner of the present age concepts related to bibliographic relationships. Barbara Tillett has defined the concept as: “*Bibliographic relationships refer to the connections and associations between two or more than two bibliographic items*” (Tillett, 1991). Tillett, in her doctoral dissertation, has given examples of bibliographic relationships such as the relation between second edition of a book with the first edition, the whole-part/part-whole relations between an item of a series as part of the whole series etc. IFLA-LRM document has pointed out that “*Relationships are an essential part of the bibliographic universe: they connect instances of entities and provide context for them*” (Riva et al., 2017).

3.1. Chronology of Bibliographic Relationships

Obviously, the purpose of this research work is to design a prototype search interface for a library to visualize bibliographic relationships and to utilize those relationships for easy navigation in discovering related objects. But before making a quantum jump into the core of this research, it is necessary to establish proper context for the framed objectives in terms of the groundbreaking theories and practices that have been formulated and implemented over the last three centuries (1841 to 2020) in managing bibliographic relationships in library catalogues.

A. Contribution of Panizzi, 1841

Lehnus in his research work (Lehnus, 1972) reported that Panizzi was aware about the existence of the concepts of bibliographic relationships and he used 'cross-references' to connect related bibliographic objects in his 91 rules through three types of cross references (name to name; name to work; and work to work). The rules of Panizzi also include provisions to connect various editions, different versions, available translations, etc.

B. Contributions of C.A. Cutter, 1876

C.A. Cutter is considered as the father of modern cataloguing and the objectives of a library catalogue that he had proposed way back in 1876 still hold true for web-OPAC. The second and the third objectives as proposed by Cutter are actually related with the collocation. The

RDC (Rules for a Dictionary Catalogue) as developed by Cutter over the years through many editions, includes provisions to link related items in printed catalogue cards like notes, 'see' references, 'see also' references, use of uniform titles to collocate all related titles etc (Cutter, 1904). In fact indication of edition, physical description etc in a catalogue entry is also considered as helpful in collocation of related documents. But Cutter had limited these linking mechanisms to support bibliographic relationships only at the 'item' level, not at the 'work' level possibly because of the fact that he had never differentiated a 'book' from a 'work' in RDC (Zhang, 2003).

C. A.L.A. Cataloging Rules, 1908

It is obvious from the objectives as reported in this code that the mechanisms for collation of the related documents were taken into consideration efficiently but only at the code level without the theories and logic in the use of linking mechanisms (Mukhopadhyay, 2005a).

D. Library of Congress Descriptive Cataloging Rules, 1949

In similar ways (like ALA cataloging rules, 1908) this cataloguing code also taken care of collocating related bibliographic objects by using the 'tracing' techniques. Later on, both AACR I and AACR II have adopted liberally the techniques of tracing in achieving collocation. But here too all the linking mechanisms were based on professional experiences without any theoretical base to guide the use of linking mechanisms (Mukhopadhyay, 2005a).

E. Contributions of Seymour Lubetzky, 1953

The contributions of Lubetzky in shaping background theories related to bibliographic relationships are of immense importance and may be viewed from different angles – i) in reshaping Cutter's objectives (which remained unchallenged for long 75 years) by placing 'collocation' as the first objective of cataloguing and then the 'finding' function; ii) in bringing back the concept of 'work' from Panizzi's rules and establishment of the fact that 'book' and 'work' are two different concepts; iii) in identifying the fact that 'a book' and 'a work' are coextensive only if the book has single edition; iv) in revealing the fact that most frequently used books in a library of any type or size are having multiple editions, different editors, variants title information, multiple authorships, many translations, different series, different translators and thereby a library catalogue needs to differentiate concepts of 'book' and 'work'; and v) in paving the path for later research works in managing bibliographic relationships (Zhang, 2003).

F. Contributions of Barbara Tillett, 1987

Barbara Tillett has formalized bibliographic relationships in her doctoral research to answer three major research questions - i) is there any theoretical base for bibliographic relationships and if not, is it possible to develop one that can guide cataloguers in managing such relationships? ii) how and to what extent physical forms of library catalogues influenced the evolution of bibliographic relationships? and iii) is it feasible to extend the theoretical base of bibliographic relationships in machine-readable catalogues (that time OPAC was the newest physical form

of a library catalogue)? The answers to these interrelated research questions have developed the base for seven taxonomical bibliographic relationships (Tillett, 2001) as discussed in section 3.2.

G. Contributions of Richard P. Smiraglia, 1992

Smiraglia in his doctoral research has extended the categories of bibliographic relationships as formulated by Tillett in 1987 through the following findings – i) the second category of bibliographic relationships i.e derivative relationships (as advocated by Tillett) occurs more often than other categories of bibliographic relationships for ‘works’ in the humanities; ii) there are different types of distinctive derivative relationships; and iii) it is quite possible to develop a taxonomy of derivative relationships.

The above seven theoretical works are considered as the groundbreaking research activities in the domain of bibliographic relationships that paved the path of new cataloguing objectives (to explore/to navigate); new cataloguing principles (principles of bibliographic relationships); new bibliographic data models based on bibliographic relationships (FRBR, IFLA-LRM, BIBFRAME, etc); and new cataloguing code (RDA).

3.2 Types of Bibliographic Relationships

In continuation with the previous section, this section covers the taxonomical categories of bibliographic relationships as formalized by Tillett in 1987 and as fine tuned by Smiraglia in 1992.

The Tillett’s categories are as follows:

- Equivalence relationship (copies, issues, facsimiles, photocopies, microforms, and other similar reproductions);
- Derivative relationship (variations, versions, editions, revisions, translations, adaptations, paraphrases, etc);
- Descriptive relationship (description, criticism, evaluation, or review of that work, including annotated editions, casebooks, commentaries, critiques, etc.);
- Whole-part/Part-whole relationship (a component part of a bibliographic item/work, a selection from collection/series);
- Accompanying relationship (including supplements, concordances, indexes, catalogs, etc.);
- Sequential relationship (different titles of a serial, monographic sequels, item of a series, etc); and
- Shared characteristic relationship (not otherwise related but having same author, common title, same subject or other features which can be used as an access point).

Smiraglia on the basis of his findings (see section 3.1:G) has proposed that derivative relationship (that occurs more frequently in humanities) may be extended to include following seven sub-categories:

Simultaneous derivations (two editions published simultaneously and having slender differences in intrinsic bibliographic characteristics);

- Successive derivations (successive editions, revisions, revised editions with new authors);
- Translations (translated works including those with the original text);
- Amplifications (illustrated texts, musical settings, and criticisms, concordances and commentaries with the original text);
- Extractions (abridgements, condensations, excerpts etc);
- Adaptations (simplifications, screenplays, other modifications);
- Performances (audio only or audio-visual recordings)

3.3 Managing Bibliographic Relationships in Traditional Catalogue

Tillett in her research work had not only identified seven categories of bibliographic relationships but she had also reported the linking devices that were in use to support inherent bibliographic relationships in the then prevailing physical form of a catalogue. These were - Main entry, Uniform title, Added entry, Dash entry, Analytical entry, Multilevel description, Edition statement, Series statement, Physical description, Note, Reference entries. She had pointed out the use of hypertext link and integrated record displays from shared data available in databases in case of machine-readable form of a catalogue as instances of bibliographic relationships. However, she had categorically identified linkage devices for each type of bibliographic relationship -

- Equivalence— Dash entry; notes; uniform title;
- Derivative— References; dash entries for added editions; edition statements; notes; uniform titles; cross references; subject headings; common main entries; filing titles; added entries;
- Descriptive— Notes; common main entry; added entries; subject entries;
- Whole-Part— Contents notes; analytical entries; added entries; multilevel description; dash entries; uniform titles; explanatory references;
- Accompanying— Addition to physical description; notes; dash entries; multilevel description; separate record with linking notes;
- Sequential— Notes; added entries; uniform titles;
- Shared Characteristic— Same access point; language; publisher; date.

In 2001, it has been opined by Tillett (Tillett, 2001) that the existing cataloguing rules (in AACR II specially) though can cover almost all forms of equivalent relationships but are not quite accommodative to link certain derivative relationships (like adaptations, change of genre,

free translation etc) and a few descriptive relationships (like review, casebook, criticism, annotated editions etc). It means that a library doesn't have any cataloguing rules to support or view bibliographic relationship between *Godaan* by Premchand (published in 1936) with the working paper by Harshida R. Chauhan entitled *Godan: A Criticism of Novel by Premchand* (published in 2019). Tillett has graphically represented her view of cataloguing rules cut-off point in establishing bibliographic relationships (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Cataloguing rules and Bibliographic relationships [source: Tillett, 2001]

4. Bibliographic Relationships and Modern Cataloguing Theories

The domain of library cataloguing is presently passing through a rapid phase of transformation. This core area of knowledge organization is now all set to enter into the 3rd generation from 2nd generation (dominated by AACR II and MARC 21 family of bibliographic data standards originated from MARC II project). The emergence of new cataloguing objectives (the FRBR objectives based on the work of Svenonius (Svenonius, 2000); new cataloguing principles (IME/ICC principles); new bibliographic data models (IFLA-LRM, BIBFRAME and XOBIS);

and the new cataloguing code (RDA) are all acting as forces at the back-end to support this shifting of generation. Moreover, the concept of GLAM (Galleries-Libraries-Archives-Museums) is making libraries a part of the bigger picture where cultural objects and bibliographic objects are viewed as interrelated parts of a single knowledge organization framework (for example the CCO – Cataloguing Cultural Objects data model). In each of the ongoing changes, as mentioned above, relationships between entities in general and bibliographic relationships in particular are considered as one of the most important components of the bibliographic universe. The following eight sections (4.1 through 4.8) discuss in brief the treatment of bibliographic relationships in data models, data formats, cataloguing code level development, global initiatives, and a transformation of theoretical base of biblio-cultural relationships.

4.1. Principles of Bibliographic Relationships

Mukhopadhyay in his courseware for IGNOU in 2005 reported (Mukhopadhyay, 2005a) that the principles of bibliographic relationships as proposed by Velluci (Vellucci, 1997b) may act as the guideline for future activities related to bibliographic relationships. These principles are as follows:

- **Principle of Relationship Identification:** The essences of this principle are - a) all important bibliographic relationships exists between the entity being described and other entities within or outside of the bibliographic database should be identified; b) provision must be made for independent & dependent relationships; and c) identification should be bidirectional in nature.
- **Principle of Enabling Linkage:** The substances of this principle are – a) related bibliographic records are to be linked; b) nature of relationship must be identified; and c) linkage between bibliographic records needs to be bidirectional.
 - **Principle of Multi-level Description:** The kernels of this principle are – a) cataloging code/rules must support independent description of an entity at several levels; b) both abstract work(s) and physical object(s) should be covered; and c) should support hierarchical relationships in multilevel.
- **Principle of Consistency:** The issues related with this principle are – a) identification and linkage of bibliographic relationships should be consistent; b) linkage must be independent of physical formats; and c) navigation between related objects must be enabled and should work consistently.

4.2 Relationships in Bibliographic Data Models

Bibliographic data model era started with the ISDBs in the decade of seventies, but with the progress of library technologies like RDBMS, E-R data modeling, Object-oriented data models etc ISDBs have lost their importance simply because of the fact that these can support only

flat-file data structure, not the relational data modeling to take the full advantages of the back-end RDBMSs that most library management software adopted. The E-R data modeling era in the domain of bibliographic description has been started with FRBR in 1998 with the arrival of FRBR data elements (attributes), FRBR entities (under three groups) and the bibliographic relationships between the entities within the group and with entities belonging to other groups (IFLA Study Group on the Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records & International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, 1998). According to FRBR model there are three primary bibliographic relationships in the group I entities - *<realized_through>* relationship connecting work and expression; *<embodied_in>* relationship connecting expression and manifestation; and *<exemplified_by>* relationship connecting manifestation and item. The following four bibliographic relationships dominate the group II - *<created_by>* connects person or corporate body to work; *<realized_by>* points person or corporate body to expression; *<produced_by>* links person or corporate body to manifestation; and *<owned_by>* joins person or corporate body to item. In the group III, the *<has_as_subject>* relationship ensures that all relevant works to a given subject are linked together (Mukhopadhyay, 2005b). The later standards like FRAD, FRSAD, grand unification of these three models (FRBR, FRAD, FRSAD) in IFLA-LRM and BIBFRAME 2.0 have also treated bibliographic relationships with the same importance as done in FRBR. It is also evident from research reports that IFLA-LRM is a much more comprehensive bibliographic data model in comparison with BIBFRAME 2.0 (Aalberg et al., 2019).

Fig. 3: Relationships in bibliographic data models [source: Aalberg et al., 2019]

4.3. Relationships in Biblio-cultural Data Models

Biblio-cultural information space is a reality now. The success of such complex unification requires smart data structures. In recent times three such groundbreaking initiatives are leading us from bibliographic universe to GLAM world. These are – a) CCO (Cataloguing Cultural Objects); b) CIDOC-CRM (Conceptual Reference Model); and c) EDM (Europeana Data Model). CCO has adopted ER data modeling techniques to link authority datasets (name authority, place authority, concept authority and subject authority) with ‘work’ records and other related objects (image, source etc). Both CIDOC-CRM and EDM have adopted FRBR (Object-oriented FRBR) for linking related objects from bibliographic universe and cultural-heritage world. A closer look of these three conceptual models shows that bibliographic relationships as proposed in FRBR have great influence on these frameworks (Zapounidou et al., 2017).

4.4. Treatment of Relationships in Bibliographic Data Formats

The machine-readable cataloguing world is dominated by three standard data formats namely UNIMARC, CCF and MARC 21 (a family of five coordinated standards). In all of these three global bibliographic data standards, researchers have found that there are three categories of bibliographic relationships - a) Vertical – hierarchical relationship/part-whole or whole-part; b) Horizontal – versions of a ‘work’ available in different languages, formats, media etc share this kind of relationships; and c) Chronological – relationship between successive issues. Pat Riva reported that these three categories of relationships in MARC can easily be mapped with Tillett’s taxonomy of bibliographic relationships e.g. MARC chronological relationship is equivalent to Tillett’s sequential relationship; MARC vertical relationship is similar to Tillett’s whole-part / part-whole relationship; and MARC horizontal relationships is analogous to Tillett’s derivative relationship (Riva, 2013).

4.5. Treatment of Relationships in Metadata Schema

The way bibliographic world is dominated by content designators (UNIMARC/CCF/MARC), the digital library world is dominated by metadata schemas. These metadata schemas can be divided into two broad categories – generic schema and domain-specific schema. The Dublin Core Metadata Elements Set (DCMES) is considered as the De-facto global standard in the group of generic metadata schema. The domain-specific schemas are meant for a given discipline or a given format e.g. VRACore is a metadata schema for images, FGDC is a schema for geographical data objects and so on. It is important to note that most of the domain-specific schemas include main 15 elements of DCMES (as common minimum data elements) to remain compatible for semantic mapping and retrieval. The Dublin Core metadata standard has an element called DC.Relation, which is meant to identify the related resource(s) and link those resources through this metadata element preferably by means of a URI or by using a formal

identification system (DCMI Usage Board, 2020). There are six pairs of relations (bidirectional in nature) defined at this time -

- IsPartOf / HasPart; IsVersionOf / HasVersion; IsFormatOf / HasFormat; References / IsReferencedBy; IsBasedOn / IsBasisFor; and Requires / IsRequiredBy.

4.6. Treatment of Relationships in RDA

The bibliographic universe in RDA centres around two basic elements – entities and their relationships. The bibliographic relationships are a principle that governs RDA but initially those were appendices not chapters (Appendices I through M). In recent times RDA (in beta toolkit) has upgraded bibliographic relationships as ‘relationship elements’ (a relationship element relates two entities) and then it has been updated as ‘relationship matrix’. In July 2020, RDA has again changed the provision and has placed bibliographic relationships under each entity (a much helpful rearrangement in place of the previous relationship matrix). The snapshot from RDA beta toolkit (in Fig. 4) shows this restructuring of relationships (RDA beta toolkit - <https://beta.rdatoolkit.org>):

Fig. 4: Relationships structure in RDA: Manifestation to Manifestation [source: RDA beta toolkit]

4.7. Bibliographic Relationships in Practical Implementations

OCLC has initiated a number of projects to implement bibliographic relationships as tools for enhanced retrieval such as FictionFinder, Algorithm, Extending the Case of Clinker, FRBRization of Humphry Clinker and Work Records in WorldCat. However, the project FictionFinder requires special mentioning because of the scalability of the initiative. The project has clustered 2.9 million bibliographic records (fiction books, eBooks, and audio materials) into works (<https://experimental.worldcat.org/xfinder/fictionfinder.html>). The other global services like Trove (from National Library of Australia) has successfully applied mechanisms to group together all editions (different manifestations) under the related ‘work’ (Fig. 5).

Fig.5: Bibliographic relationships in Trove – 4 editions grouped under the ‘work’ [source:<https://trove.nla.gov.au/>]

4.8 Bibliographic Relationships through Graph Theory

The latest theoretical development in the domain of bibliographic relationships has been initiated once again by Barbara Tillett, who first formalized bibliographic relationships in her doctoral research way back in 1987. Ronald J. Murray and Barbara B. Tillett have proposed in their

research paper (Murray & Tillett, 2011) that bibliographic relationships can be described with the help of graph theory. Authors of this seminal paper have pointed out the following needs in resource description keeping in view the rapid advances in library technologies – a) identifying and describing the objects (bibliographic and cultural) and their relationships must be based on some theoretical guidance; b) the present theoretical base originated from ER (Entity-Relation) and OO .

Fig. 6: WEMI relationships through a common node [source: Murray & Tillett, 2011]

(Object-Oriented) data modeling have several constraints in identifying and describing bibliographic relationships; and c) the limitations of ER and OO modeling in resource description can be removed by using a “graph-friendly” theory. The graph theory as proposed by Euler in 1736 is now regarded as a sub-discipline under mathematics and has wide array of applications in computer science, social sciences, linguistics, biology and other domains under science and technology. In the domain of library and information science, there are many applications of graph theory in scientometrics, informetrics, webometrics and semantic information retrieval. The most interesting part of the theory as proposed by Murray & Tillett is that the entire FRBR based bibliographic relationships can be represented by using a graph with the help of a common node (Fig. 6). The WEMI (Work-Expression-Manifestation-Item) can be connected with each other through a common node ‘C’ in the diagram given in Fig. 6. The relationships are bidirectional in nature – R1 represents *<is_a_realization_of>* and R2 expresses *<is_realized_through>* relationships in between Work and Expression; R3 stands for *<is_an_embodiment_of>* and R4 expresses *<is_embodied_in>* relationships in between Expression and Manifestation; and R5 represents *<is_an_exemplification_of>* and R6 shows *<is_exemplified_by>* relationships in between Manifestation and Item.

5. Research Questions

“There is nothing more practical than a good theory”. (Kurt Lewin)

The previous two sections have represented briefly the journey of cataloguing theories in managing bibliographic relationships over the last 175 years and have also established the fact that the importance of bibliographic relationships is increasing rapidly in this era of technology-driven library systems. This fact is reflected both in the emerging bibliographic data models and in the latest cataloguing codes. Additionally, the emergence of biblio-cultural information space, which is represented by the concept of GLAM, and the new user task of a library catalogue as proposed in IFLA-LRM (‘to explore’) to support navigation on the basis of bibliographic relationships are two critical factors in designing and developing library search systems with the provision of – a) visualization of bibliographic relationships; b) navigation through bibliographic relationships; and c) discovery of related resources on the basis of bibliographic relationships.

In view of this background and the objectives as given in section 2, this research work aims to solve following three research questions (RQs):

- RQ1 Is it possible to design a digital archive containing bibliographical objects (e.g. document like books, journal article etc) and related cultural objects (e.g. book cover image, pictures, illustrations etc) with the provision to support visualization of bibliographic relationships and navigation on the basis of the identified relationships to discover related resources?
- RQ2 How, and to what extent, is it feasible to extend the relationships-driven navigation mechanisms to support retrieval of related biblio-cultural resources available in Indic-scripts in a Unicode-compliant environment?
- RQ3 What should be the theoretical base for the prototype digital archive of cultural text? Is it possible to extend the theory as proposed by Murray & Tillett at the practical level? What data standards should be adopted for the archive? Is there any standard open source digital library solutions that can support this experiment? What are the additional steps require achieving the objective 3 as stated in section 2?

6. Methods and Tools

These interlinked RQs are directing towards a series of tasks that are required for the completion of the design of the prototype digital archive to support relationships based navigation in addition to the general searching and browsing facilities. The five-point methodology may be explained as below:

Table 1: Tasks Groups and Steps

Group	Steps	Decisions table /Criteria
Group A Theoretical foundation	1. General theory	Graph theory
	2. Theoretical base for displaying bibliographic relationships	Theoretical base as proposed by Murray & Tillett in 2011 where a common node can be used to connect biblio-cultural resources
	3. Tools selection	To be selected on the basis of criteria set for theoretical base and digital library software
Group B Collection building	4. Language & Script selection	Bengali-script based documents
	5. Documents selection	Classic Bengali novels with cover page illustration done by a renowned artist/painter
	6. Types of novels and illustrations	Only copyright free novels and illustrations to be considered to avoid legal complications
Group C Organizational mechanism	7. Selection of data format for bibliographic objects	DCMES to be selected as it is the global defacto standard as generic metadata schema
	8. Selection of data format for cultural objects	VRACore to be selected as the globally agreed upon metadata schema for image description
	9. Selection of relationship designator	DC.Relation is the automatic choice with its six pair of bidirectional relationship
Group D Tools and Platform selection	10. Software and standards selection	Only open source software and open standards to be deployed
	11. Digital archive software selection	Omeka is the automatic choice because of its wide acceptance in the cultural institutions of the world and default support for qualified DCMES and VRACore
	12. Platform selection	Ubuntu LTS 20,04 with Apache 2.4.41, MariaDB 10.5 and PHP 7.4
Group E Visualization and navigation	13. Relationship support tool	Cytoscape.js: graph theory based visualization
	14. Relationship graph display	Dagre: directed acyclic graph for Cytoscape.js
	15. Navigation	Cytoscape-panzoom : pan and zoom for graphs generated by Cytoscape.js

7. Features of the Navigational Framework

The prototype as developed by using the methodology involving five distinct groups and fifteen interrelated steps may be viewed from three angles – a) how two groups of resources (bibliographic objects and cultural objects) are organized and related in real-time; b) how does the framework support visualization; and c) how does it help to discover related resources through navigation.

The organization mechanisms include four set of activities – configuration of relationships rules; metadata encoding for bibliographic resources through qualified DCMES; metadata encoding for cultural resources through VRACore; and linking related resources to support grouping of the connected resources and visualization of the relationships in real-time. The relationship rules can be created on the basis of the theoretical base adapted and the only mandatory parameter is that the relationship must be bidirectional – here `frbr:creator` / `frbr:creatorOf` (Fig. 7):

The screenshot displays a web-based configuration interface for FRBR (Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Relationships) rules. At the top, there are tabs for '5', 'frbr:creator', 'frbr:creatorOf', and '0'. The main form area is titled 'Source Rule' and contains a dropdown menu set to 'Rule 2: Reference with subject People'. Below this, there are two columns of input fields: 'Source Name' (containing 'frbr:creator') and 'Source Label' (containing 'Created_By'). The 'Target Rule' section has a dropdown menu set to 'Rule 1: Reference'. Below it, 'Target Name' is 'frbr:creatorOf' and 'Target Label' is 'Created'. There are empty text input fields for 'Directives' and 'Ancestry'. At the bottom left, there are 'Update' and 'Remove' buttons. At the bottom right, there are 'Add Relationship Type' and 'Edit Relationship Rules' buttons.

Fig. 7: Formulation of relationships rules on the basis of FRBR

The linking of related resources from two groups of objects (bibliographical textual objects and related cultural objects in the form of images) encoded in two different metadata schemas is accomplished through defined relationships (as shown in Fig 7.). The linking of a primary resource (available in Bengali language with item id #405) with three related resources under different relationships types is demonstrated in Fig. 8. It shows how cover page image (id #407), image of author (id #406) and image of the artist/illustrator of the cover page (id #410)

are linked in the framework. It also shows how the defined relationships can be picked up from the drop down list to identify relationships between two objects. The visualization features and the navigational framework originated from the activities discussed above and illustrated through corresponding snapshots (Fig. 7 and Fig. 8) are described through Fig. 9 to Fig. 12 (given in Appendix). The Fig. 9 shows the availability of relationship-driven navigational facility in the retrieval interface of the prototype digital archive of cultural text. The primary reference here is a classic novel in Bengali (id #405). It provides a thumbnail of related objects (bibliographic and cultural) through a relationship graph in the right panel of the search interface with an option to 'enlarge' the relationship navigation window. The thumbnail window for relationships shows link to three objects. The (2) inside the window indicates that two related objects along with the type of relationships can be viewed in detail and the third object displayed is the image of the artist responsible for the cover page image of the novel (the image of the artist encoded in VRACore). A click on the 'enlarge' link opens a pop-up window (light box in technical term) as shown in Fig.10. It displays in closeup (inside a lightbox) the primary reference (id #405) encoded in qualified DCMES is linked with the author (image of the author encoded in VRACore as an cultural object) and the cover page image (encoded in VRACore).

Fig. 8: Linking of related resources in the framework

At this point, the navigation framework allows an end-user to travel the path either through the cover page image or through the author image according to his/her need. If s/he wishes to navigate through the cover page image all the related objects of third order (not related directly to the primary reference id #405 i.e. the novel) are displayed in a graph-friendly environment portraying the biblio-cultural relationships these objects share with each other (Fig. 11). The graph in Fig. 11 demonstrates the primary reference (with id #405) in central place with relationships links to cover page image and author image. The cover page image shows link to the artist who illustrated it and (6) indicates that the said artist has six more paintings in the digital archive of cultural text. A click to (6) leads the end-user to a complex relationship graph where all six paintings are linked to the artist and the artist is linked with the cover page image of the novel from where the user has started his/her navigational journey in the digital archive (Fig. 12).

8 . Conclusion

The discussions held in section 6 and 7 along side the features of the navigational framework as demonstrated in the appendix (Fig. 9 to Fig 12) on the basis of biblio-cultural relationships make it clear that the objectives of this research work as framed in section 2 and the research questions as formulated in section 5 are well achieved and well answered respectively. This prototype digital archive of cultural text in Bengali language is a small one with only five hundred objects (bibliographic and cultural) but shows clearly that the emerging theoretical framework of biblio-cultural relationships can be implemented at the practical level. The graph-friendly theory of biblio-cultural relationships as proposed by Murray & Tillett has a far reaching consequence in developing futuristic models related to resource description activities and in designing enhanced retrieval interface for end users to support the newly introduced user task in IFLA-LRM i.e 'to explore' on the basis of bibliographic relationships to discover related objects.

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Appendix

তিতাস একটি নদীর নাম

Dublin Core

Title
তিতাস একটি নদীর নাম

Subject
বাংলা সাহিত্য - উপন্যাস

Description
তিতাস একটি নদীর নাম অক্ষয় মন্ডল রচিত বিখ্যাত উপন্যাস, লেখকের মৃত্যুর পাঁচ বছর পর প্রকাশিত। এই একটি উপন্যাস লিখে লেখক খ্যাতি অর্জন করেন। এই উপন্যাসে গ্রামের দরিদ্র মাঝে শ্রেণীর লোকজনের দুঃখ-দুর্দশার কাহিনী ফুটিয়ে তুলেছেন। পরবর্তীকালে এই উপন্যাস অবলম্বনে চলচ্চিত্র নির্মিত হয়।

Creator
অক্ষয় মন্ডল

Publisher
পুথির

Date
১৯৫৮

Relationships
Enlarge

Date Added
January 29, 2020

Collection
ClassicBengal

Item Type
Text

Citation
অক্ষয় মন্ডল রচিত 'তিতাস একটি নদীর নাম'

Fig. 9: Visualization of bibliographic relationships in retrieval interface with 'Enlarge' option

Fig. 10: Navigation facility in a lighbox triggered by 'Enlarge' option

Fig. 11: Navigation facility leads to related resources linked with the primary resource connected through different relationships

Fig. 12: A complex relationship graph depicting the entire related resources in navigational framework